

Reaction of 2-Mercapto-4-chloro-6-bromobenzimidazole with Chloroacetic acid, α -Halogenoketones and Alkyl Bromides

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The syntheses of 6-bromo-8-chlorothiazolo[3,2-*a*]benzimidazol-3(2*H*)-one (4), 3-aryl-6-bromo-8-chlorothiazolo[3,2-*a*]benzimidazoles (6), 2,3-dihydro-6-bromo-8-chlorothiazolo[3,2-*a*]benzimidazole (7) and 4*H*-2,3-dihydro-7-bromo-9-chloro[1,3]thiazino[3,2-*a*]benzimidazole (8) have been achieved starting from 2-mercapto-4-chloro-6-bromobenzimidazole (2). Compound 2, obtained by the reaction of 4-bromo-6-chloro-1,2-diaminobenzene (1) with carbon disulphide, on condensation with chloroacetic acid gives the acid 3, which on cyclisation with acetic anhydride furnishes 4, and not the other isomer 9 as revealed by pmr spectral data. Condensation of 2 with α -halogenoketones followed by PPA cyclisation of the intermediate ketone (5) yields 6. Similarly, the reaction of 2 with 1,2-dibromoethane and 1,3-dibromopropane gives 2,3-dihydro-6-bromo-8-chlorothiazolo[3,2-*a*]benzimidazole (7) and 4*H*-2,3-dihydro-7-bromo-9-chloro[1,3]thiazino [3,2-*a*]benzimidazole (8), respectively.

THE syntheses of 6-bromo-8-chlorothiazolo[3,2-*a*]benzimidazol-3(2*H*)-one (4), 3-aryl-6-bromo-8-chlorothiazolo[3,2-*a*]benzimidazoles (6), 2,3-dihydro-6-bromo-8-chlorothiazolo[3,2-*a*]benzimidazole (7) and 4*H*-2,3-dihydro-7-bromo-9-chloro[1,3]thiazino[3,2-*a*]benzimidazole (8) reported in the present communication, were undertaken to study the directive influence of bromine and chlorine atoms on cyclisation of their precursors. 2-Mercapto-4-chloro-6-bromobenzimidazole (2) obtained by the treatment of 3-chloro-5-bromo-1,2-diaminobenzene (1) with carbon disulphide, when condensed with chloroacetic acid gave 4-chloro-6-bromobenzimidazol-2-thiolacetic acid (3). The acid (3), being unsymmetrical is expected to give 6-bromo-8-chlorothiazolo[3,2-*a*]benzimidazol-3(2*H*)-one (4), or 5-chloro-7-bromothiazolo[3,2-*a*]benzimidazol-3(2*H*)-one (9) or both depending upon the direction of cyclisation. The acid (3), however, when heated in a mixture of acetic anhydride and pyridine underwent cyclisation furnishing a single product (tlc). The appearance of a band at 1735 cm^{-1} ($\text{N}-\text{C}=\text{O}$) in the ir spectrum of the TLC-pure product confirmed the cyclisation. Further confirmation that the cyclisation did occur comes from the mass spectrum of this compound which showed the isotopic cluster of molecular ion peaks at m/z 302 (P), 304 (P+2) and 306 (P+4) indicating the presence of one atom of bromine and one atom of chlorine and supports the molecular formula. The structure 4 has been finally assigned to this TLC-pure product on the basis of pmr spectral data in preference to 9.

The reaction of 2-mercapto-4-chloro-6-bromobenzimidazole (2) with 1,2-dibromoethane gave a

single product (tlc) which could be represented either by structure 7 or 10. In either of the structure the signals at 7.71 and 7.77 may be due to H_A and H_B (not necessarily), respectively. It may be noted that H_A and H_B resonate in close proximity, the difference between the two signals (7.77-7.71) is 0.06 Hz. In structure 9, both the aromatic protons (H_A and H_B) will resonate in close proximity to each other as observed in 7 (or 10), whereas in 4, H_A will be deshielded by the thiazolidinone ring and as a result H_A will resonate at downfield in respect to the other proton, H_B . The deshielding has its origin in the magnetic anisotropy of the carbonyl group with minor contribution from the rest of the thiazolidinone ring. Comparison of the chemical shifts of H_A in 7 (or 10) having a value at δ 7.71 (or 7.77) and the signal at δ 8.24 (a value sufficiently higher than 7.71 or 7.77, and is due to the deshielding effect of the carbonyl group) exhibited by the cyclised product obtained from the acid (3) supports the structure 4. Such a downfield shift would not be expected from the structure 9. The other proton H_B resonate at δ 7.84 and the difference in chemical shifts of H_A and H_B (8.24-7.84) is 0.40 Hz. The magnetic anisotropic effect of similar carbonyl group has been found to deshield the *peri*-protons^{1,2} to an appreciable extent. After having established the structure 4, the structure 7 (and not 10) for the product obtained from the reaction of 2 with 1,2-dibromoethane was assigned on analogy with structure 4. The exhibition of isotopic cluster of molecular ion peaks at m/z 288 (P), 290 (P+2) and 292 (P+4) indicating the presence of one bromine and one chlorine atoms supports the molecular formula.

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2-Mercapto-4-chloro-6-bromobenzimidazole (2) on condensation with α -halogenoketones yielded ketones (5) (ν_{\max} 1655-1670 cm^{-1} , C=O) which on treatment with PPA underwent cyclisation giving a single compound (tlc) in each case. Ir (absence of carbonyl band) and pmr (one proton singlets at δ 7.36 and 7.26 due to C₂-H exhibited by the cyclized product obtained from 5 (R=C₆H₅) and 5 (R=*p*-H₃C-C₆H₄), respectively) spectra confirmed the tlc-pure product to have a cyclic structure. The cyclisation had indeed occurred was further confirmed by mass spectral data. The exhibition of isotopic cluster of molecular ion peaks at *m/z* 362 (P), 364 (P+2) and 366 (P+4) and 376 (P), 378 (P+2) and 380 (P+4) in the mass spectra of the compounds obtained from the cyclisation of 5 (R=C₆H₅) and 5 (R=*p*-H₃C-C₆H₄), respectively indicates the presence of one bromine and one chlorine atoms and supports the molecular formulae. But the pmr and mass spectral data were not of much help in deciding in favour of either structure 6 or 11, the formation of which are possible during the cyclisation of ketone 5, because of its unsymmetrical nature. Assignment of structure 6 was, however, based on analogy with the structure 4.

(1) CS₂, KOH; (2) ClCH₂CO₂H, NaOAc, (3) Ac₂O, pyridine, (4) RCOCH₂Br, (5) PPA, (6) BrOH₃CH₂CH₂Br, (7) BrOH₃CH₂CH₂Br.

Similarly, 2-mercapto-4-chloro-6-bromobenzimidazole (2) on reaction with 1,3-dibromopropane furnished a tlc-single product to which structure 4*H*-2,3-dihydro-7-bromo-9-chloro[1,3]thiazino[3,2-*a*]benzimidazole (8) has been assigned on the analogy with structure 4. Here also the appearance of one

multiplet centred at δ 2.67 integrated for two protons (-SCH₂CH₂CH₂N-), two triplets, at 3.48 and 4.93 each integrated for two protons (SCH₂ and NCH₂, respectively) two doublets each integrated for one proton at 7.68 and 7.73 (aromatic protons H_A and H_B not necessarily, respectively) in the pmr spectrum of the product obtained from the reaction of 2 with 1,3-dibromopropane, suggests that the cyclisation had indeed occurred, although the pmr spectral data were not of much help in deciding the location of bromine and chlorine atoms in the tlc-pure product.

Fungicidal tests: For fungicidal assay, the method of Aytoun *et al.*⁹ was used. *Aspergillus flavus*, *Candida albicans*, *Microsporium gypseum* and *Nocardia asteroides* were used as test fungi. Among the compounds screened, compound 4 and 6 (R=*p*-H₃C-C₆H₄) were found to possess activity against *Candida albicans* and *Nocardia asteroides* at 1:500 dilution; 7 against *Candida albicans*, *Microsporium gypseum* and *Nocardia asteroides* at 1:500 dilution.

Antibacterial tests: For antibacterial test, the Rideal-Walker⁴ serial drop dilution method was used. The test organisms were 24 h old culture of *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli*. Compounds 4, 6 (R=*p*-H₃C-C₆H₄) and 7 were found to possess activity against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* at 1:500 dilution.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. Tlc was performed on silica gel plates using acetone-benzene (1:3) as the solvent system. Ir spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Beckman IR-20 spectrophotometer. Pmr spectra were run on a Perkin-Elmer 90 MHz spectrometer using TMS as the internal reference standard. Mass spectra were scanned on Hitachi RMU-6 spectrometer.

3-Chloro-5-bromo-1,2-diaminobenzene (1): 2-Chloro-4-bromoacetanilide obtained from *o*-chloroaniline by acetylation and subsequent bromination, on nitration followed by hydrolysis yielded 2-chloro-4-bromo-6-nitroaniline, m.p. 117° (lit⁶. 117-18°). The nitroaniline on reduction with Raney nickel and hydrazine hydrate, following the usual procedure furnished the desired diamine (1) which was immediately used for the preparation of mercapto-benzimidazole (2).

2-Mercapto-4-chloro-6-bromobenzimidazole (2): It was synthesised in 60% yield by the reaction of 3-chloro-5-bromo-1,2-diaminobenzene (1) with carbon disulphide following the method of Van Allan and Deacon⁶ for the synthesis of 2-mercaptobenzimidazole, m. p. >300° (EtOH-DMF) (Found: S, 12.22; N, 11.09. C₇H₄N₂BrClS requires S, 12.14; N, 10.62%); ν_{\max} 1180, 1195 (C=S), 1600 (C=N), 3040 and 3420 cm^{-1} (N-H).

4-Chloro-6-bromobenzimidazo-2-thiolacetic acid (3). A mixture of 2-mercapto-4-chloro-6-bromobenzimidazole (2; 2.63 g, 0.01 mol), chloroacetic acid (0.96 g, 0.01 mol) and potassium hydroxide (0.56 g, 0.01 mol) in ethanol (100 ml) was heated, under reflux, for 3 h. The reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature, acidified with dilute acetic acid and kept overnight. The white solid, thus separated, was filtered and washed with water. Crystallisation from ethanol furnished white needles (2.0 g, 62%), m.p. 221° (Found S, 10.32; N, 8.94. $C_9H_8N_2BrClSO_2$ requires S, 9.95; N, 8.70%); ν_{max} 1610 (C=N), 2660-2700 (COOH) and 3070 cm^{-1} (N-H bonded).

6-Bromo-8-chlorothiazolo[3,2-a]benzimidazol-3(2H)-one (4). 4-Chloro-6-bromobenzimidazo-2-thiolacetic acid (3, 1.0 g) in a mixture of acetic anhydride (1.0 ml) and pyridine (3.0 ml) was heated on a steam bath for 15 min. The reaction mixture was kept overnight and the solid, thus separated, was filtered, washed with water and finally crystallised from ethanol as white flakes (0.5 g, 53%), m.p. 251° (Found S, 10.83; N, 9.62; M^+ at m/z 302, 304 and 306 showing the presence of one bromine and one chlorine atoms. $C_9H_8N_2BrClSO$ requires S, 10.54; N, 9.22%; mol. wt. 303.5); ν_{max} 1500 (C-N), 1570, 1605 (C=N) and 1735 cm^{-1} (C=O), δ (TFA- $CDCl_3$) 4.75 (2H, s, CH_2), 7.84 (1H, d, H_B , J_{AB} 2Hz), 8.24 (1H, d, H_A , J_{AB} 2Hz).

2-p-Methylphenacylthio-4-chloro-6-bromobenzimidazole (5, R= p - $H_3C-C_6H_4$). A mixture of 4-chloro-6-bromo-2-mercaptobenzimidazole (2; 1.315 g, 0.005 mol) and p -methylphenacyl bromide (1.665 g, 0.005 mol) in anhydrous ethanol (30 ml) and DMF (30 ml) was heated, under reflux, for 6 h. The reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature and the hydrobromide, thus separated, was neutralised with sodium carbonate. The free base, so obtained, was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from ethanol to furnish pale yellow needles (1.2 g, 60%), m.p. 280° (Found: S, 8.42; N, 7.47. $C_{16}H_{12}N_2ClBrSO$ requires S, 8.09; N, 7.07%); ν_{max} 1600 (C=N), 1665 (C=O) and 3320 cm^{-1} (N-H).

Similarly, 5 (R= C_6H_5), m.p. 220° (Found: S, 8.63; N, 7.60. $C_{15}H_{10}N_2BrClSO$ requires S, 8.39; N, 7.34%); ν_{max} 1590 (C=N), 1670 (C=O) and 3260 cm^{-1} (N-H) was prepared in 52% yield.

3-p-Tolyl-6-bromo-8-chlorothiazolo[3,2-a]benzimidazole (6, R= p - $H_3C-C_6H_4$): A mixture of 2-p-methylphenacylthio-4-chloro-6-bromobenzimidazole (5, R= p - $H_3C-C_6H_4$; 1.0 g), phosphorus pentoxide (4.0 g) and orthophosphoric acid (3.0 ml) was heated on an oil bath at 150-60° for 3 h. The reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature, poured into ice-cold water and neutralised with sodium carbonate. The solid, so obtained, was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from ethanol as light brown needles (0.5 g, 52%), m.p. 255° (Found: S, 8.25; N, 7.83; M^+ at m/z 376,

378 and 380 showing the presence of one bromine and one chlorine atoms. $C_{16}H_{10}N_2BrClS$ requires S, 8.47, N, 7.41%; mol. wt. 377.5); ν_{max} 1550 (C-N stretching) and 1600 cm^{-1} (C=N, C=C), δ (TFA- $CDCl_3$) 2.58 (3H, s, CH_3), 7.26 (1H, s, C_2-H) and 7.40-7.84 (6H, m, Ar-H)

Similarly, 6 (R= C_6H_5), m.p. >300° (Found S, 8.72, N, 7.31; M^+ at m/z 362, 364 and 366 showing the presence of one bromine and one chlorine atoms. $C_{15}H_9N_2BrClS$ requires S, 8.80, N, 7.70%; mol. wt. 363.5), ν_{max} 1515 (C-N) and 1605 cm^{-1} (C=N and C=C), δ (TFA- $CDCl_3$) 7.36 (1H, s, C_2-H), 7.64-7.88 (7H, m, Ar-H), was prepared in 42% yield.

2,3-Dihydro-6-bromo-8-chlorothiazolo[3,2-a]benzimidazole (7) A mixture of 2-mercapto-4-chloro-6-bromobenzimidazole (2; 1.315 g, 0.005 mol) and 1,2-dibromoethane (0.94 g, 0.005 mol) in anhydrous ethanol (30 ml) was refluxed for 6 h. The reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature and poured into ice-cold water and basified with sodium carbonate. The free base, thus obtained, was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from ethanol giving light brown needles (0.8 g, 53%), m.p. 170° (Found S, 11.41, N, 10.29, M^+ at m/z 288, 290 and 292 showing the presence of one bromine and one chlorine atoms. $C_9H_8N_2BrClS$ requires S, 11.05; N, 9.66%; mol. wt. 289.5); ν_{max} 1560 and 1605 cm^{-1} (C=N); δ (TFA- $CDCl_3$) 4.34 (2H, t SCH_2), 5.06 (2H, t, NCH_2), 7.71 (1H, d, H_A or H_B , J_{AB} 2.0 Hz) and 7.77 (1H, d, H_B or H_A , J_{AB} 2.0 Hz).

4H-2,3-dihydro-7-bromo-9-chloro[1,3]thiazino[3,2-a]benzimidazole (8): A mixture of 2 (1.315 g, 0.005 mol) and 1,3-dibromopropane (1.01 g, 0.005 mol), anhydrous ethanol (30 ml) and DMF (30 ml) was heated, under reflux, for 5 h. The reaction mixture was poured into cold water and neutralised with ammonium hydroxide. The solid, thus obtained, was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from ethanol as white crystals (0.7 g, 46%), m.p. 155-56° (Found: S, 10.15; N, 9.30. $C_{10}H_8N_2BrClS$ requires S, 10.54; N, 9.22%); ν_{max} 1565 (C-N stretching) and 1600 cm^{-1} (C=N); δ (TFA- $CDCl_3$) centred at 2.67 (2H, m, $SCH_2CH_2-CH_2N$), 3.48 (2H, t, SCH_2), 4.93 (2H, t, NCH_2), 7.68 (1H, d, H_A or H_B , J_{AB} 2 Hz) and 7.73 (1H, d, H_B or H_A , J_{AB} 2 Hz).

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